

Selective and Rapid Extraction-Spectrophotometric Determination of Palladium(II) with 6-(2'-Hydroxyphenyl)-2,4-dithio-1-phenyl-1,3,5-triazine†

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*Manuscript received 24 August 1990, revised 14 February 1991,
accepted 6 May 1991*

THIOTRIAZINES are used as analytical reagents for the determination of palladium and copper¹. The present work describes a selective and rapid method for extraction-spectrophotometric determination of palladium(II) with 6(2'-hydroxyphenyl)-2,4-dithio-1-phenyl-1,3,5-triazine (HPDPT) using isoamyl alcohol as diluent.

Experimental

HPDPT was prepared according to the reported method². Stock solution of palladium(II) was prepared using PdCl₂ (Johnson Matthey) and standardised³.

To an aliquot of the solution containing 5–40 µg of palladium(II) in the separating funnel was added 6M HCl (1 ml) and diluted to 30 ml with distilled water. To the mixture was added the reagent (0.5 ml; 0.0025M in dimethyl formamide) followed by addition of isoamyl alcohol (10 ml). After equilibration of the phases for 30 s, the organic layer was separated, dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄ and the absorbance measured at 370 nm against reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

Amyl alcohol extract of the palladium complex showed maximum absorbance at 325 nm. However reagent blank showed negligible absorbance above 370 nm and therefore further measurements were carried out at 370 nm. The complex showed maximum and steady absorbance over 0.1–2.0M acidity. Among the various acids studied HCl was found to be suitable. A 0.5 ml of 0.002M HPDPT (in dimethyl formamide) was sufficient to extract 40 µg of Pd^{II} quantitatively in a single operation. Mole-ratio method and slope method both indicated the formation of 1 : 2 (metal : ligand) complex under the experimental conditions. System was

†Presented at the "26th Annual Convention of Chemists" held at Indore, 1989.

found to obey Beer's law over the range 5–40 μg of Pd^{II} . The effect of foreign ions on extraction of Pd^{II} was studied at 2% tolerance limit. In the estimation of 20 μg of Pd^{II} , the following ions did not interfere when present in amounts (μg shown in parenthesis): Pt^{IV} (500), Au^{III} (20), Os^{VIII} (20), Cr^{VI} (2000). No interference was observed even upto 3000 μg each of Rh^{III} , Ru^{III} , Ir^{IV} , Ag^{I} , Cu^{II} , Fe^{II} , Fe^{III} , Ni^{II} , Pb^{II} , Hg^{II} , Co^{II} , Cd^{II} , V^{V} , Mn^{II} , Al^{III} , Ca^{II} , Mg^{II} and Bi^{III} . Among the anions tested presence of 5000 μg each of F^- , Br^- , CO_3^{2-} , HCO_3^- , PO_4^{3-} , $\text{B}_4\text{O}_7^{2-}$, CN^- , acetate, tartrate and EDTA had no diverse effect, whereas NO_2^- (250), SO_3^{2-} (2500), SCN^- (1600), oxalate (3000) and citrate (3000) were tolerated; I^- , $\text{S}_2\text{O}_3^{2-}$ interfered seriously.

The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity were calculated to be $1.01 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $0.01 \mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$ respectively. The average of 10 determinations of 20 μg of Pd^{II} in 10 ml isoamyl alcohol was 20.05 μg with a standard deviation of 0.28.

The method was applied for the estimation of palladium in Pd-charcoal spent catalyst. The mean of three determinations of the amount of palladium was found to be 8.39% whereas by standard method³ it was found to be 8.47% with a relative error of 0.82%. The method was also applied for synthetic mixtures having compositions, (i) Pt, 65; Rh, 15; Ru, 15; Pd, 5 and (ii) Pt, 80; Pd, 8; Au, 2; Ag, 3; Rh, 3, Ir, 4%. The mean of three determinations of the amount of palladium was found to be 4.96% and 7.92% respectively. The method was thus found to be selective and rapid for the determination of palladium with commonly associated metals.

References

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